

Post-Quantum Secure UE-to-UE Communications

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Abstract—The rapid development of quantum computing poses a significant threat to the security of current cryptographic systems, including those used in User Equipment (UE) for mobile communications. Conventional cryptographic algorithms such as Rivest–Shamir–Adleman (RSA) and Elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) are vulnerable to quantum computing attacks, which could jeopardize the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of sensitive data transmitted by UEs. This demo paper proposes the integration of Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) in TLS for UE Communication to mitigate the risks of quantum attacks. We present our setup and explain each of the components used. We also provide the entire workflow of the demo for other researchers to replicate the same setup. By addressing the implementation of PQC within a 5G network to secure UE-to-UE communication, this research aims to pave the way for developing quantum-resistant mobile devices and securing the future of wireless communications.

Index Terms—Post-quantum Cryptography, UE Security, Cellular Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum computing poses a significant threat to the security of modern cryptographic systems, including those used in mobile communications. User Equipment (UE) such as smartphones and other wireless devices rely heavily on cryptographic protocols for secure communication, authentication, and data protection [1]. However, the cryptographic algorithms commonly used in UE, such as Rivest–Shamir–Adleman (RSA) and Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC), are vulnerable to attacks by sufficiently powerful quantum computers. These attacks, which exploit algorithms such as the Shor algorithm [2], could break the underlying mathematical problems on which these cryptographic methods are based, rendering them ineffective.

Therefore, the advent of quantum computing necessitates the development and integration of Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) in UE. PQC comprises a set of cryptographic algorithms that are believed to be resistant to attacks from both classical and quantum computers [3]. These algorithms leverage mathematical problems that are considered difficult for even quantum computers to solve, providing a more robust foundation for security in the quantum era [4]. The integration of PQC in UE poses a particular challenge due to the limited resources of mobile devices, such as limited computing power, memory, and battery life. Another hurdle is ensuring compatibility with existing network infrastructure and protocols. However, the potential benefits of PQC in safeguarding user data and privacy in the face of quantum threats make it an important area of research.

This paper leverages the recent advances in PQC to enable secure and scalable interactions between UE in a 5G testbed. The testbed demonstrates the practical application of these technologies by showcasing real-time post-quantum secure communication among UE devices. Specifically, it uses Kyber/ML Key Encapsulation Mechanism (KEM) [5], a NIST-standardized KEM, for key management over TLS. By integrating the Kyber with wolfSSL, we illustrate the process for establishing secure communication channels resistant to quantum attacks between UEs in a virtual 5G setup developed using Open5gs and UERANSIM. The research aim is to establish the groundwork for the development of quantum-resilient mobile devices that ensure the security and privacy of user data in the upcoming era of quantum computing.

II. 5G BASED TESTBED FOR PQC ANALYSIS

In order to display our approach in this paper, we use Dell Desktops equipped with an i7 CPU with 20 cores, 32 GB RAM, and 512 GB SSD storage. We deploy different components of this setup in separate virtual machines (VMs) on the KVM hypervisor. The operating system used in each VM is Ubuntu Server version 20.04.6 LTE. Each VM has 4 GB of memory and two CPU cores. We use Open Vswitch (OVS)¹ to set up and manage the virtual network interfaces and bridges required to simulate the connections between different network components.

A. 5G Testbed

For the 5G setup, we use open-source technologies such as UERANSIM and Open5Gs. UERANSIM² is the simulator for 5G UE and gNodeB (gNB), while Open5GS³ is a project that provides a complete 5G Core (5GC) network implementation and enables testing and development of 5G networks. The components are deployed in various VMs. The most critical components of the 5G-based testbed are described below:

UE: These are devices such as smartphones, tablets, IoT devices, etc., that are connected to the network. UERANSIM is used to create a realistic simulation environment. We use two UEs, one of which acts as a server and the other as a client. However, these two UEs can also work in reverse. UERANSIM provides a TUN interface to utilize the UE's internet connectivity.

¹Online: <https://github.com/openvswitch/ovs>, Available: July 2024

²Online: <https://github.com/aligungr/UERANSIM>, Available: July 2024

³Online: <https://github.com/open5gs/open5gs>, Available: July 2024

Fig. 1. 5G simulation environment used within the demo

gNB: The Next Generation Node B, gNB for short, manages the radio access portion of the network and provides an interface that connects UEs to the 5G core network. UERANSIM is also used here to simulate the 5G gNB and test the connectivity and performance of 5G communication with UEs.

Core Network: The 5G Core (5GC) is responsible for various tasks within the mobile network and enables communication. The 5G Core network is cloud-native and fully software-based, enabling greater agility and flexibility when deploying on different cloud infrastructures. Two main planes characterize the architecture: the User Plane (UP) and the Control Plane (CP). The CP is responsible for managing the signaling and network functions required to establish and maintain sessions, manage mobility, and enforce policies, while the UP manages the actual traffic to ensure the transmission of user data. Key components of CP are (i) AMF (Access and Mobility Management Function) authenticates the UE and establishes a connection. When a user moves between different cells or networks, AMF handles the handover process to ensure continuous connectivity. (ii) SMF (Session Management Function) establishes a data session and sets up an interface with the UPF (User Plane Function), which is the central component of UP and serves as the gateway to data network (DN) for user traffic. This function is responsible for packet forwarding, routing, and traffic shaping. UP also includes the DN, which consists of application servers, Internet access, and other services through which the UE communicates. CP includes other functions such as PCF (Policy Control Function), UDM (Unified Data Management), and UDR (Unified Data Repository).

In this setup, UE, gNB, CP, and UP have been deployed in four different VMs. The setup is shown in the Figure 1. First, each UE connects to the network using the AMF, which sets up authentication and authorization. A PDU(Packet Data Unit) session is then established, with the SMF configuring the UPF for data processing. During data transmission, a data

unit, known as a data packet, is transmitted from UE1 to the gNB. The gNB then transmits the data packet to the UPF via the GTP-U protocol. The UPF forwards the packet via the DN to the other UPF, which serves the gNB of UE2. The gNB at the destination then transmits the packet to UE2. If both UEs are in the same local network, it may not be necessary to include a DN. Instead, the UPF can manage the local routing.

B. PQC Secured Communication

The Open Quantum Safe (OQS) project is a publicly available initiative to facilitate the transition to cryptographic methods, resistant to quantum computing [6]. OQS provided liboqs⁴, a publicly available C library that provides cryptographic algorithms that are resistant to quantum attacks. wolfSSL⁵ is a light version of OpenSSL, an alternative SSL/TLS library. The wolfSSL team integrates experimental PQC algorithms, such as Kyber, into the wolfSSL library. In this experiment, the wolfSSL library is used to establish TLS connections, and the liboqs library is used to generate Kyber keys in both UEs, as indicated in Figure 1. It can be noted that wolfSSL enables the use of post-quantum signature algorithms, such as Dilithium or Falcon, for authentication. However, this work is specifically centered around quantum-safe key exchange.

III. DEMO WORKFLOW

The sequence diagram of the quantum-safe UE-to-UE communication experimented in this paper is shown in Figure 2. The most important steps in this demo are described below:

(i) **UE Registration:** First, the UEs are registered on the 5GC via the WebUI application. Then we run the configuration files of the UEs in UERANSIM, and both UEs (UE1 and UE2) send registration requests to the gNB, which serves as an intermediary between the UEs and the core network and is shown as VM3 in Figure 1. The gNB transmits these registration requests to the core network (VM1), where authentication and authorization take place. The core network validates the credentials of each UE and sends confirmation messages to the gNB after successful authentication. The gNB then sends these confirmation signals to UE1 (VM4) and UE2 (VM5), thereby completing the registration process and establishing a secure connection to the network. It is important to note that the scope of this study does not include the integration of Kyber during UE registration, rather it focuses on its integration during TLS establishment for the key exchange which begins with the following steps.

(ii) **Key Pair Generation:** To generate the Kyber key pairs, both UEs use the liboqs library after completing the registration process. The generation of key pairs is crucial for ensuring secure communication, as these keys are used for secure key exchange during the TLS handshake, encapsulating and decapsulating symmetric keys that are then used for session encryption. UE1 and UE2 generate their public and private keys autonomously by executing the Kyber key

⁴Online: <https://github.com/open-quantum-safe/liboqs>, Available: July 2024

⁵Online: <https://github.com/wolfSSL/wolfssl>, Available: July 2024

Fig. 2. Kyber/ML KEM enabled UE to UE Communication

generation function provided by liboqs, as shown in the first steps in Figure 2.

(iii) TLS Handshake Initialization: To further secure the communication, UE1 initiates a TLS 1.3 handshake by sending a Client Hello message to UE2. After receiving the Client Hello message, UE2 responds with a Server Hello message. These messages exchange critical cryptographic information such as public key/ciphertext, certificates, etc., as shown in Figure 2 with a dotted line to indicate that this information is contained in the ClientHello and ServerHello packets and has already been exchanged [7], [8]. This handshake ensures that both UEs agree on the cryptographic parameters and establish initial security parameters that are proposed in RFC 8446 ⁶ **(a) Public Key Exchange:** In this experiment, Kyber is used in the key exchange phase of TLS. To create a secure communication channel, UE1 and UE2 share their public keys over the 5G network using the secure channels established during the registration process. In this testbed, UE1 transmits its public key to UE2, and in return, UE2 sends its public key to UE1. This key sharing allows each UE to use the other party's public

key for subsequent cryptographic procedures, as described in RFC 8446 ⁷. **(b) Certificate Exchange:** During this stage, UE1 and UE2 exchange digital certificates to mutually verify and validate their respective identities. UE1 sends its certificate to UE2 and UE2 sends it to UE1 (RFC 5280) [9].

(iv) Shared Secret Generation: Shared secrets are generated by both UEs by utilizing the Kyber with the exchanged public keys and their respective private keys. UE1 utilizes the public key of UE2 and its own private key to create a shared secret and a corresponding ciphertext. UE2 utilizes the received ciphertext and its private key to obtain the identical shared secret. The shared secret is an essential element in the establishment of a secure communication channel using the Kyber KEM. The library used in the experiment, liboqs, supports Kyber/ML-KEM in both hybrid and conventional modes, as well as varying security levels.

(v) Shared Secret Derivation: The shared secrets are derived by both UEs based on the information exchanged during the TLS handshake. The derivation process results in shared keys that are used for the encryption and decryption of the subsequent communication.

(vi) Handshake Completion: After the successful derivation of the session secrets, the handshake is completed, and a Kyber-enabled secure communication channel is established, as presented with a sky blue line in Figure 2.

(vii) Secure Message Exchange: Now that the secure communication channel has been set up, UE1 and UE2 can exchange encrypted messages. Each message is encrypted and digitally signed before sending, decrypted, and validated after receipt. Using Kyber PQC guarantees that security and privacy are maintained throughout the communication process, effectively safeguarding against the risks posed by future advances in quantum computing.

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⁶Online: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc5280>, Available: May 2008

⁷Online: <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/rfc8446/>, Available: Mar 2020